

Nanomaterials synthesized by Pulsed Plasma in Liquid: their Characterizations, Properties and Applications

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Abstract:

Graphene sheets with modified surface by sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) surfactant, using the simple and one-pot solvothermal reaction method. Solvothermal method is based on a chemical reaction between initial substances, mainly, the solvent and dissolved substances in it. Solvothermal reaction is generated inside stainless steel autoclave, under temperature and pressure conditions, in definite duration of time.

Gold nanoparticles have been attracting big attention due to their extensive application in many fields such as chemistry, physics, material science, electronics, catalysis and bionanotechnology. Medical applications of gold nanoparticles have been tested in biomedicine and surgery, *in vitro* biosensing, *in vivo* imaging, drug delivery, and tissue engineering (Kim et al. 2015), therapy and imaging. Other applications of gold nanoparticles are including sensing and antibacterial were also reported recently.

During synthesis of pure iron NPs one of the electrodes was connected to a vibrator in order to keep discharge process continuous. We did not use any additives (surfactants or other agents) in the liquid. A magnetic stirring bar at the bottom of the reactor with a rotational speed of 900 rpm mixed the immiscible solutions sufficiently to reduce the particle aggregation. Before starting the experiments, the glove box atmosphere was purged of oxygen (O₂) using nitrogen gas as a safety measure to prevent fire.

Graphene nanocomposites was obtained by stainless steel autoclave (capacity of 100 ml) fixed to the metal equipment body, and was connected with temperature controller. Initial substances (total volume 60 ml), composed of solvent (distilled water-ethanol mixture with 3:1 volume ratio), pure carbon powder 0.3 g (purity 99.9%, purchased from Kojundo Kagaku. Co.), sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) surfactant (C₁₂H₂₅NaO₄S, 5% solution, purchased from Kanto Chemical Co.) were placed inside the stainless steel autoclave and covered with lid. Solvothermal reaction temperature was set at 170°C with further increase of inner-autoclave pressure to 1.4 MPa. For the synthesis of fusiform gold nanoparticles, we have applied pulsed plasma which was generated between two gold metal rod shaped electrodes submerged in hexane solution. Energy of the simple impulse was applied with electrical energy of 0.05 Joule, capacity of the condensator was 4 μFs (microfarads).

The purity and dispersity of the Fe phase gradually increased (48–98 %) with decreasing concentration of toluene, and the size of nanoparticles decreased (21–9.5 nm) with decreasing toluene concentration. These results suggest that by changing the medium composition, we can control the phase composition and size of forming materials. XRD results indicated that the samples were α-Fe nanoparticles with bcc structure, Im-3 mspace group, and cell parameter of a = 0.2927 nm. Multilayer graphene sheets consisting of hexagonal honey-comb lattice were revealed by HRTEM analyses. Fusiform gold nanoparticles were successfully synthesized by using the pulsed plasma in a liquid method. TEM observations of as-synthesized sample clearly showed formation of fusiform gold nanoparticles with a length of 50 to 150 nm and diameter of 5 to 15 nm.

Keyword:

Nanoparticles, HRTEM, XRD, TEM, gold nanoparticles

Heterovalent Coordination Compounds Of Iron And Their Biological Activity

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Abstract:

School of physics and of chemistry of the Tajik National University for more than 50 years explores the processes of complex formation in the system Fe (II)-Fe (III)-one, polybasic carboxylic, amino acids, neutral ligands of classical method of the oxidation potential of Clark Nicholas at various concentration terms, ionic strength of solutions and temperatures. The regularities of formation of complexes of different composition and stability are revealed, their equations are derived, and coefficients are calculated. For calculations the general equation of oxidative potential and oxidative function of Professor Yusupov are used, which consider the influence of 8 variables, thermodynamic parameters of processes are determined. Reliable, most accurate results are obtained, as evidenced by the data of statistical processing of experimental data using various modern computer programs. For example, in the Fe (II)-Fe (III)-acetic acid-water system, complexes of the following composition are formed: $[\text{FeL}]_2^+$; $[\text{FeL}]^+$; $[\text{FeL}_2]^+$; $[\text{FeL}_2(\text{OH})]_0$ $[\text{FeIIFeIII}_2 \text{L}_6(\text{OH})_2]^+$ and $[\text{FeL}]^+$, where: L - acetate-ion.

Analysis of experimental dependences, compilation of chemical models of existing equilibria in solutions and determination of numerical values of model parameters (constants of formation, domains of domination, maximum degrees of accumulation, thermodynamic functions) show that in the studied systems the most stable complexes are heterovalent coordination compounds that contain one or more hydroxyl groups. In all the above systems, heterovalent mixed-ligand hydroxocomplexes begin to form at pH above 4.5 and dominate almost to pH 10.5. Recently received the results of perchlorate in the environment and certain concentrations of the base particles show that heterovalent mixed-ligand iron hydroxocomplexes can dominate even up to pH 13.

According to the calculated molar fractions (degrees of accumulation) of the resulting complexes, diagrams of their distribution on the pH scale are constructed, the analysis of which allows to develop optimal conditions for the allocation of certain coordination compounds. The complexes developed according to the appropriate methods are used in conjunction with the relevant specialists for their further research on various plants, crops, large, small cattle, birds. All the coordination compound has biological activity, according to all indicators give an increase compared to the control, but the most effective among the tested complexes were heterovalent hydroxyacetateiron complex of composition: $[\text{FeIIFeIII}_2 \text{L}_6(\text{OH})_2]^+$. According to the results of such studies, 8 patents were obtained.

Keyword:

Oxidative potential, thermodynamic functions, constants of formation, hydroxocomplexes, Clark Nicholas

Inverse Molecular Docking as a Novel Approach to Study Anti-carcinogenic and Anti-neuroinflammatory Effects of Curcumin

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Abstract:

Research efforts are placing an ever increasing emphasis on identifying signal transduction pathways related to the chemopreventive activity of curcumin. Its anticarcinogenic effects are presumably mediated by the regulation of signaling cascades, including NF- κ B, AP-1, and MAPK. By modulating signal transduction pathways, curcumin induces apoptosis in malignant cells, thus inhibiting cancer development and progression. Due to the lack of mechanistic insight in the scientific literature, we developed a novel inverse molecular docking protocol based on the CANDOCK algorithm. For the first time, we performed inverse molecular docking of curcumin into a collection of 13,553 available human protein structures from the Protein Data Bank resulting in prioritized target proteins of curcumin. Our predictions were in agreement with the scientific literature and confirmed that curcumin binds to folate receptor beta, DNA (cytosine-5)-methyltransferase 3A, metalloproteinase-2, mitogen-activated protein kinase 9, epidermal growth factor receptor and apoptosis-inducing factor 1. We also identified new potential protein targets of curcumin, namely deoxycytidine kinase, NAD-dependent protein deacetylase sirtuin-1 and -2, ecto-5'-nucleotidase, core histone macro-H2A.1, tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type 11, macrophage colony-stimulating factor 1 receptor, GTPase HRas, aflatoxin B1 aldehyde reductase member 3, aldo-keto reductase family 1 member C3, amiloride-sensitive amine oxidase, death-associated protein kinase 2 and tryptophan-tRNA ligase, that may all play a crucial role in its observed anticancer effects. Moreover, our inverse docking results showed that curcumin potentially binds also to the proteins cAMP-specific 3',5'-cyclic phosphodiesterase 4D and 17- β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 10, which provides a new explanation for its efficiency in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. We firmly believe that our computational results will complement and direct future experimental studies on curcumin's anti-cancer activity as well as on its therapeutic effects against Alzheimer's disease.

Keywords:

Curcumin, anti-carcinogenic effects, anti neuroinflammatory effects, mechanistic insights, inverse molecular docking

The Papeutic Properties Of Coordination Compounds Of Iron With Organic Ligands

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Abstract:

At the Department of physical and colloid chemistry of the Tajik national University for many years, together with the research centers of Moscow, St. Petersburg, the processes of formation of coordination compounds of vital metals: iron, zinc, copper, cobalt, manganese, Nickel with single, multi-basic organic acids, amino acids, neutral polydentate ligands are studied. Spectral and potentiometric methods have been studied formation and domination of coordination compounds of these metals in a wide range of pH, temperature, ionic forces of solutions. The classical method of the oxidation potential of Clark -Nicholski used to study a variety of redox systems. For processing of experimental data, we used modern mathematical techniques, functions, e.g., oxidative function, Yusupov and the computer program "Excel", "Sigma Hlot -10". The obtained results are used to develop optimal conditions for the formation of heterovalent coordination compounds that can be models of living systems and plants. Studies of chemical and biological properties of heterovalent coordination compounds have shown that the most stable and effective are heterovalent complexes of $[FeIIFeIII2 L6(OH)2(H2O)10]0$ (L-ligand of acetic acid), as well as $[FeIIFeIII2(H2O)6]^-$ (L3--ligand of citric acid).

Acetic acid (CH_3COOH) - monobasic, therefore, it coordinates with the Central atoms of complexing agents in the form of a monodentate ligand CH_3COO^- . With citric acid harder. In the acidic range of pH (2-4), the ligand can be monodentate – $(HOOCCH_2)_2C(OH)COO^-$ in pH increases bidentate – $(-OOCCH_2)(HOOCCH_2)C(OH)COO^-$, and then, in an alkaline medium, tridentatum – $(-OOCCH_2)(-OOCCH_2)C(OH)COO^-$. In a highly alkaline environment, above pH of 12.5 with corresponding concentration parameters of citric acid can be chetyrehmagnitnoy, i.e., coordination can be by the hydroxyl group. Therefore, depending on the pH of the medium, we obtained heterovalent complexes with different composition of ligand citrates.

On the atomic adsorption analyzer we studied the composition of these herbs. It is established that they contain elements such as calcium, potassium, iron, copper, phosphorus, zinc, nitrogen, and even in small amounts of silver, gold. Moreover, the content of phosphorus and calcium is the highest. In recent years, quite often for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, allergies, stress relief and depression, fatigue salts are used (better sea) for baths. The effectiveness of therapeutic baths is significantly increased when added to the salts of fragrant herbs. Therefore, the synthesized coordination compounds were used as micro-additives to bath salts together with local herbs: peppermint, Basil, juniper fruits and rose petals, which contain a large number of aromatic esters. Patents have been obtained for the proposed compositions of bath salts. On the atomic adsorption analyzer we studied the composition of these herbs. It is established that they contain elements such as calcium, potassium, iron, copper, phosphorus, zinc, nitrogen, and even in small amounts of silver, gold. Moreover, the content of phosphorus and calcium is the highest.

$[FeIIFeIII2 L6(OH)2(H2O)10]0$; $[FeIIFeIII2(H2O)6]^-$. Pharmacological tests were carried out. The results showed that the used heterovalent coordination compounds increase the effectiveness of the components of the salt composition for therapeutic baths, they can be used in cosmetology for removing spots on the skin, relieving allergic itching

Keywords:

Coordination compounds, multi-basic, Sigma Hlot -10, Clark -Nicholski, Ionic forces

Mycobacterium tuberculosis DnaG primase as an essential drug target – A Computational Approach

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Abstract:

Tuberculosis (TB) is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, infecting and killing millions of people. With growing multiple drug resistance (MDR) and extensive drug resistance (XDR) along with the prolonged current TB treatment it becomes necessary to examine novel drug targets in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb) for discovering new drugs to combat the disease. DnaG primase, an important drug target has a crucial role in the initiation of DNA replication. Its catalytic Toprim domain was modeled in the study. Further, three distinct chemical libraries were screened *in silico* to identify the best scored compounds against the Toprim domain. Four compounds were identified and further analysed for ADMET properties. Additionally, 50 ns molecular dynamics simulations were carried out of these compounds in complex with Toprim domain to check their stability. It was also observed that the amino acids Lys 101, Glu 137, Asp 188 were responsible for forming the hydrogen bonded interactions with the screened drug like compounds. Hence the identified drug-like compounds could serve as anti-TB leads that need further wet lab validation.

Keywords:

DnaG primase, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, Homology Modeling, *in silico* Screening, Molecular Dynamics Simulations

Figure 1: Docked complex of daunorubicin and modeled Toprim domain in surface representation showing the hydrogen bonded interactions with Lys 101, Tyr 102 and Glu 137.

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Synthesis and Anti-cancer Evaluation of Amide Derivatives of Pyridines as Anticancer Agents

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Abstract:

A series of amide derivatives of pyridine (10a-j) have been synthesized and its chemical structures were confirmed by ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and mass spectral data. Further, these compounds were tested for their preliminary anticancer activity against four different human cancer cell lines such as MCF-7 (breast), A549 (lung), DU-145 (prostate) and MDA MB-231 (breast) by MTT assay and etoposide used as standard drug. All these derivatives exhibited well to moderate activity compare to standard drug. Among them, four compounds (10b, 10c, 10h and 10j) were showed more potent activity.

Keywords:

Cancer, biologically active heterocyclic compounds, pyridine and anticancer activity

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Antidiabetic activity of ethanolic extract of *Homalium zeylanicum* Benth bark against Streptozotocin induced diabetic rats

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Abstract:

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder that has become increasingly common worldwide. There is several insulin as well as oral hypoglycemic agents under trade for the management of diabetes; however, its use leads to various side effects. Therefore, identification of natural products having antidiabetic activity with least side effects becomes immense importance nowadays. Aim and Objectives: The present investigation is aimed to evaluate the anti-hyperglycemic effect of ethanolic extract of *Homalium zeylanicum* Benth (HZEE) in streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetic rats. Methods: EEHZ was undergoes the preliminary phytochemical screening using standard methods and HPTLC method used for identification of active principles. *In vitro* antioxidant studies were evaluated by using DPPH and Nitric oxide radical scavenging assay. *In vivo* anti diabetic activity was evaluated against STZ induced diabetic rats. Diabetes was induced by administration of STZ (55 mg/kg, i.p.). The diabetic rats were treated with HZEE (200 and 400 mg/kg, p.o., respectively) for 21 days. Fasting blood glucose level and body weight were monitored every 7 days during the treatment. At the end of the study serum was collected for analysis of biochemical parameters, liver was isolated for estimation of hepatic key enzymes; pancreas was isolated for study of histopathological changes. Results and discussion: After treatment with EEHZ fasting blood glucose, HbA1c levels, SGPT, SGOT, Total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, triglycerides levels, Fructose 1,6 phosphatase and glucose 6 phosphatase levels were significantly decreased in diabetic rats. However, haemoglobin, HDL cholesterol, total protein, glucose 6 phosphate dehydrogenase, SOD, GSH and CAT levels were significantly increased in EEHZ treated diabetic rats. The histopathological studies of the pancreas in extract treated diabetic groups revealed almost normal appearance. HPTLC analysis confirms the presence of Betulinic acid in HZEE. Conclusion: The results indicated that significant antidiabetic effect of HZEE in STZ induced type II diabetic rats without toxicity.

Design, Eco-Friendly Synthesis And Anticancer Activity Of Quinazoline Derivatives

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Abstract:

Synthesized three component one pot synthesis of Quinazoline derivatives by condensation of 2-aminopyrimidines, substituted aromatic aldehydes and ketones in the presence of toluene by conventional and reflux and by microwave irradiation, catalyzed by Trifluoromethanesulphonic acid and other catalysts. By using chromatography techniques the compounds purified and characterized by using different spectroscopic techniques like FTIR, Mass Spectroscopy, NMR, XRD and SEM analysis. The compound showed promising activity on PC-3 Prostate Cancer cells. However, at the studied concentration this compound was found to be not active on colon, CNS, Ovarian, Renal and Breast and melanoma cancer types. On PC-3 prostate cancer cell types this compound showed better effects with overall cell growth of 77.36%. However, this compound did not demonstrate any anticancer effects on CNS, melanoma, Ovarian, Renal and breast cancer cell types.

Keywords:

Microwave synthesis, Prostate cancer, Breast and melanoma cancer types.

RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for the Determination of Hydrochlorothiazide, Amlodipine besylate and Telmisartan Hydrochloride Multicomponent API and Tablet dosage form in Biorelevant Media (FaSSIF)

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Abstract:

A simple, rapid, and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method for simultaneous analysis of Hydrochlorothiazide (HTZ), Amlodipine besylate (AML) and Telmisartan hydrochloride (TLM) in a tablet dosage form and in Biorelevant media has been developed and validated. This method was performed with a thermosil C18 (4.6 × 100 mm i.d., 3.7 µm particle column with 40:60 (v/v) 20mM potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer : methanol as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. UV detection at 248 nm; HTZ, AML and TLM were eluted with retention times of 1.823, 2.639, and 4.198min, respectively. The method was continued and validated accordance with ICH guidelines. Validation revealed the method is rapid, specific, accurate, precise, reliable, and reproducible. Calibration curve plots were linear over the concentration ranges 6.25-100µg/mL for HTZ, 2.5-40µg/mL for AML, and 20-320µg/mL for TLM. Limits of detection (LOD) were 0.004, 0.0016, and 0.0128µg/ml and limits of quantification (LOQ) were 0.013, 0.0052, and 0.0416µg/mL for HTZ, AML and TLM respectively. Statistical analysis was proves the method is suitable for the analysis of HTZ, AML and TLM as a bulk, in tablet dosage form and in biorelevant media without any interference from the excipients. It was also proved study for degradation kinetics of three drugs. It may be extended for its estimation in plasma and other biological fluids.

Keywords:

Hydrochlorothiazide (HTZ), Amlodipine besylate (AML) and Telmisartan hydrochloride (TLM), RP-HPLC, Validation, FaSSIF.

Figure 1: Chromatogram of HTZ, AML, and TLM at 248nm from Tablet dosage form (Telma AM H)

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In-Silico Design, Eco-Friendly Synthesis And Anticancer Activity Of Pyrazolo Pyrimidines Derivatives

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Abstract:

Inspired by the biological profile of Pyrazolo Pyrimidines and their importance in pharmaceutical field it was thought worth while to synthesize the titled compounds with a view to obtain certain chemical entities with active pharmacophore Morphological screening of 2A.50, 2A.52 (a-h) molecules against A549 and MCF-7 Cell lines. Series of pyrazolo Pyrimidines which were characterized using NMR, Mass and IR Spectral techniques prior to use for morphological study. As a part of anti-cancer evaluation, we have screened all 30 newly synthesized molecules of Pyrazolo (1,5-a) Pyrimidines against morphological behavior of A549 and MCF-7 cells. Cells were observed for 24, 48, 72 hrs, after treatment of test molecules. The MTT Cell Viability Assay Kit provides a convenient, sensitive, quantitative and reliable assay for determining the number of viable cells in a given culture. DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) is a fluorescent stain that binds strongly to A-T rich regions in DNA. When bound to double-stranded DNA, DAPI has an absorption maximum at a wavelength of 358 nm (ultraviolet) and its emission maximum is at 461 nm (blue). From the docking study, it is clear that the pyrimidine, rings are surrounded by various binding cavities . These interactions underscore the importance of nitrogen atoms for binding and subsequent inhibitory capacity. The maximum PLP score is -59.508942 kcal/mol and minimum -17.296096 kcal/mol with root mean square standard deviation (RMSD). Few of them posses good binding affinity when compare with the standard drug sunitanib maximum PLP score is -62.074202 kcal/mol.

Keywords:

Docking study, Pyrazolo Pyrimidines, Morphological screening, DAPI, A549 and MCF-7 Cell lines

Protective effects of ursolic acid against gamma irradiation induced injury through NF- κ B pathway

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Abstract:

This study was aimed to evaluate the possible protective effects of ursolic acid (UA) against gamma radiation induced damage both in vitro as well as in vivo. It was noted that the exposure to gamma radiation dose- and time-dependently caused a significant decrease in the cell viability, while the treatment of UA attenuated this cytotoxicity. The production of free radicals including ROS and NO increased significantly post-irradiation and further induced lipid peroxidation and oxidative DNA damage in cells. These deleterious effects could also be effectively blocked by UA treatment. In addition, UA also reversed gamma irradiation induced inflammatory responses, as indicated by the decreased production of TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β . NF- κ B signaling pathway has been reported to be a key mediator involved in gamma radiation-induced cellular damage. Our results further demonstrated that gamma radiation dose-and time-dependently enhanced NF- κ B DNA binding activity, which was significantly attenuated upon UA treatment. The post-irradiation increase in the expression of both phospho-p65, and phospho-I κ B α was also blocked by UA. The treatment of UA was also found to significantly prolong overall survival in mice exposed to whole body gamma irradiation, and reduce the excessive inflammatory responses. Given its radioprotective efficacy as described here, UA as an antioxidant and NF- κ B pathway blocker, may function as an important pharmacological agent in protecting against gamma irradiation-induced injury.

Keywords:

Radiation, ursolic acid, NF- κ B, TNF- α , NO.